

STRATEGIC DECISION-MAKING IN UNCERTAINTY: INTEGRATING FORWARD-LOOKING SCENARIO PLANNING AND MULTI-CRITERIA ANALYSIS FOR ADAPTIVE REUSE PROJECTS

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ABSTRACT

Background and aim. Adaptive reuse enhances circularity by repurposing buildings, reducing carbon emissions, and preserving heritage. However, decision-making is complex due to stakeholder conflicts, regulations, and uncertainties. This study introduces an integrated framework combining Cross-Impact Balance (CIB) analysis, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), and Fuzzy-TOPSIS to support structured, participatory decision-making.

Methods and Data. A mixed-method approach integrates CIB for scenario development, AHP for stakeholder-driven prioritization, and Fuzzy-TOPSIS for ranking reuse scenarios. A hypothetical case study demonstrates the framework's applicability.

Findings. The integration of CIB, AHP, and Fuzzy-TOPSIS provides a structured decision-making approach that enhances scenario coherence, aligns decisions with stakeholder priorities, and improves scenario ranking robustness. The framework enables systematic exploration of adaptive reuse scenarios, ensuring alignment with stakeholder objectives.

Theoretical / Practical / Societal implications. Theoretically, this study advances scenario-based decision-making by integrating scenario development and decision-making approaches, addressing gaps in adaptive reuse decision frameworks. Practically, it provides policymakers, urban planners, and developers with a structured tool to navigate complex decision-making in adaptive reuse projects. Societally, it supports sustainable and inclusive urban development by fostering consistent, long-term strategies that balance environmental, economic, and social considerations.

KEYWORDS: Adaptive Reuse, Circularity, Cross-Impact Balance (CIB) Analysis, Multi-criteria Decision-Making, Scenario Planning,

1 INTRODUCTION

The adaptive reuse of buildings has become a cornerstone strategy for promoting circularity in the built environment (Foster, 2020). By repurposing existing structures, adaptive reuse significantly reduces CO₂ emissions, curbs the extraction of virgin materials, and conserves valuable resources (Shahi et al., 2020). This approach directly supports global sustainability goals and addresses critical urban challenges, including resource scarcity and environmental degradation (Conejos, 2013). However, despite its promise, adaptive reuse decision-making processes remain complex and uncertain (Yung & Chan, 2012). These projects often involve a diverse set of stakeholders with conflicting interests and must navigate a range of regulatory, economic, and technical constraints (Wilkinson, 2014). Consequently, the strategies chosen for adaptive reuse are often limited to short-term

perspectives and a narrow set of options, hindering their potential to achieve long-term sustainability and circularity (Greco et al., 2024; Vardopoulos et al., 2021). To address the intricacies and uncertainties of adaptive reuse decision-making, a range of tools and methodologies has been developed (Nedeljkovic et al., 2023). Among these, multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) models have gained considerable traction for evaluating adaptive reuse projects (Nadkarni & Puthuvayi, 2020). These models provide a structured framework for assessing and comparing alternatives by incorporating multiple criteria (Love et al., 2023). However, existing decision-making approaches tend to adopt either overly generalized frameworks; focused solely on functional reuse, or overly specific ones, which prioritize granular design considerations (van Laar et al., 2024). Both approaches often overlook the broader, long-

term objectives required to achieve true sustainability and circularity. Furthermore, most frameworks rely either on quantitative methods like cost-benefit analyses (Sanchez et al., 2019), and lifecycle assessments (Foster, 2020), or on generic qualitative approaches to evaluate the feasibility of proposed interventions (Wilkinson, 2014). While these methods offer valuable insights into resource efficiency and financial viability, they often fail to account for nuanced, context-specific factors or integrate forward-looking scenario planning essential for addressing the dynamic nature of urban development. Scenarios are particularly valuable for adaptive reuse decision-making because they offer comprehensive, future-oriented perspectives. They enable decision-makers to explore how various reuse strategies might perform under different environmental, social, and economic conditions (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). This foresight helps ensure that decisions are robust, flexible, and aligned with long-term sustainability and community goals (Bottero et al., 2022). Normative scenarios, which outline pathways to achieve specific objectives (van Notten et al., 2003), are especially relevant for adaptive reuse. They help stakeholders collaboratively develop a broad range of desirable futures, ensuring that decisions reflect shared values and strategic priorities. Despite their potential, scenario-based methods are underutilized in adaptive reuse (van Laar et al., 2024), often resulting in decisions that fail to anticipate future challenges or opportunities.

There is a pressing need for decision-making frameworks that are both future-oriented and capable of addressing the inherent uncertainty and complexity of adaptive reuse projects. Such frameworks must enable the development of nuanced, context-specific scenarios that incorporate normative objectives, reflect stakeholder priorities, and facilitate the ranking of alternatives based on quantitative and qualitative criteria. To address these gaps, this study introduces an integrated decision-making framework that combines Cross-Impact Balance (CIB) analysis with the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Fuzzy-TOPSIS methods.

This research highlights the strength of combining these methodologies into a cohesive, stepwise framework, demonstrating how they can guide adaptive reuse decision-making in a structured yet flexible manner. Using a hypothetical adaptive reuse project, the study showcases how this approach facilitates scenario development, interdependency analysis, and the evaluation of alternatives under uncertainty. The main finding illustrates how these tools can be integrated into a systematic process that supports stakeholders in collaboratively designing and prioritizing adaptive reuse scenarios. This framework offers a practical pathway for addressing the complexity of adaptive reuse while aligning decisions with long-term sustainability and social responsibility goals.

2 BACKGROUND LITERATURE

Scenario development and Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) analysis are two complementary methodologies extensively used in decision-making processes involving complex systems, such as adaptive reuse. Scenario development enables the exploration of possible futures by considering various uncertainties (Weimer-Jehle, 2023), while MCDM provides a structured framework for evaluating and ranking alternatives against multiple criteria (Saaty, 1990). The integration of these methodologies has gained significant attention, for its potential to improve decision-making outcomes by combining qualitative and quantitative insights (Stewart et al., 2013).

2.1 SCENARIO DEVELOPMENT

Scenario development is a structured approach for envisioning possible future states of a system under uncertainty. Scenarios, described as: coherent, consistent, and plausible descriptions of potential futures, are categorized as exploratory, predictive, or normative (van Notten et al., 2003). Exploratory scenarios examine possible futures based on varying assumptions, aiding in visualizing outcomes. Predictive scenarios forecast likely futures based on current trends, while normative scenarios prescribe pathways to achieve specific goals (van Notten et al., 2003). The normative approach is particularly valuable for adaptive reuse decision-making, where alignment with sustainability goals and community values is essential (Gassner & Steinmüller, 2018). Scenario development methods can be categorized into quantitative, qualitative, and mixed-method approaches, each suited to different needs. Quantitative methods rely on mathematical modeling for precision but often limit stakeholder involvement and are less effective over long-term projections, as they tend to extrapolate trends and may give a false sense of certainty (Amer et al., 2013). In contrast, qualitative methods, like Intuitive Logics (IL), excel in addressing complex issues through nuanced, context-specific insights. However, they can oversimplify systems by focusing on a limited number of uncertainties, potentially overlooking critical factors (Rowe et al., 2017).

Mixed-method approaches effectively combine the strengths of both, integrating data-driven analysis with stakeholder input to foster comprehensive discussions about future possibilities (Symstad et al., 2017). An example is Cross-Impact Balance (CIB) analysis, a semi-quantitative method that uses systems theory to model integrative and holistic scenarios (Weimer-Jehle, 2006). By employing formal logic to structure quantitative and qualitative inputs, CIB generates internally consistent narrative scenarios based on interactions among drivers of change, making it particularly suitable for complex socio-technical systems (Weimer-Jehle, 2023).

2.2 MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION-MAKING

Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) methods, such as AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process), Fuzzy TOPSIS, PROMETHEE, and VIKOR, are widely used for evaluating and ranking alternatives across multiple conflicting criteria (Sahoo & Goswami, 2023). AHP excels in hierarchically structuring complex problems, prioritizing criteria through pairwise comparisons, and aggregating stakeholder preferences into a unified priority structure, fostering consensus while respecting diverse perspectives (Saaty, 1990). Fuzzy TOPSIS, which extends the classical TOPSIS method, effectively manages vagueness and subjectivity by using fuzzy set theory to rank alternatives based on their closeness to ideal and negative ideal solutions (Chen, 2000).

Combining AHP and Fuzzy TOPSIS enhances decision-making by integrating AHP's hierarchical structuring and consistency checks with Fuzzy TOPSIS's capacity for handling uncertainty (Efe, 2016). This hybrid approach is particularly valuable for complex, uncertain environments, as it provides a structured yet flexible evaluation framework (Mathew et al., 2020). Such integrations have been applied successfully in fields like supply chain management (Patil & Kant, 2014), and urban planning (Dang et al., 2019), demonstrating their versatility and effectiveness. While the combination of AHP and Fuzzy TOPSIS effectively ranks uncertain alternatives based on stakeholder preferences, it often relies on externally provided options, highlighting the need for an integrated approach that develops and ranks scenarios concurrently.

2.3 INTEGRATION OF SCENARIO DEVELOPMENT AND MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION ANALYSIS

The integration of scenario development and MCDM addresses the limitations of each methodology when applied independently. Scenario development often lacks a structured mechanism to prioritize options within each scenario, while MCDM can be overly deterministic without considering the broader context of future uncertainties (Sahoo & Goswami, 2023). By combining these methods, decision-makers can evaluate the robustness of alternatives across different scenarios, incorporate qualitative and quantitative dimensions of uncertainty, and enhance stakeholder engagement by providing a more holistic view of decision impacts (Sahoo & Goswami, 2023).

Numerous frameworks integrate scenario development with multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM), typically following one of two approaches. The scenario-driven MCDM approach develops scenarios first and applies MCDM to rank alternatives within each scenario (Bottero et al., 2022). In contrast, the MCDM-driven approach uses MCDM criteria to shape scenarios, aligning them with decision priorities (Della Spina, 2020). These frameworks have been applied in various fields, including urban planning, supply chain management, and engineering .

However, these studies often face limitations, such as relying on a limited number of scenarios that fail to capture the full range of possibilities. Many frameworks lack consistency calculations, reducing the coherence and realism of the scenarios (Weimer-Jehle, 2006). Additionally, there is an overemphasis on predictive scenarios and mathematical models, prioritizing quantitative precision over qualitative insights and stakeholder perspectives (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). These shortcomings diminish the robustness and practical applicability of the scenarios in addressing complex challenges.

The Cross-Impact Balance (CIB) method overcomes these challenges by generating numerous consistent and plausible scenarios through a combination of qualitative and quantitative inputs (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). This makes it particularly effective for exploring complex systems. However, CIB has not been fully integrated with MCDM methods like AHP or Fuzzy TOPSIS, which excel at prioritizing and ranking alternatives. Combining these approaches offers significant potential, enabling the systematic creation, evaluation, and prioritization of scenarios within a unified framework. In a participatory setting, this integration enhances stakeholder engagement by involving them in the entire process, from scenario development to ranking, ensuring scenarios are aligned with diverse preferences and easing the adoption of the chosen scenario through consensus and trust in the outcomes.

3 STEPWISE APPROACH FOR COMBINING CROSS-IMPACT BALANCE ANALYSIS, AHP AND THE FUZZY TOPSIS METHODS

This section outlines a structured, multi-step framework tailored for decision-making in normative, uncertain, and complex contexts such as adaptive reuse projects (Figure 1). By integrating Cross-Impact Balance (CIB) analysis, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), and Fuzzy-TOPSIS methodologies, this approach effectively addresses the uncertainties inherent in adaptive reuse. It enables stakeholders to collaboratively assess, develop, and prioritize reuse scenarios, demonstrating its application through a hypothetical example of an adaptive reuse project.

3.1 STEP 1: DEFINE THE AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The first step establishes the foundation for the decision-making process by ensuring a clear understanding of the project's scope and goals. To create normative scenarios; future pathways that are achievable (van Notten et al., 2003), this step focuses on defining objectives that will guide subsequent scenario development. Stakeholders collaborate to articulate the overarching goal and themes, identify desired objectives, and determine the criteria

necessary to evaluate progress toward these objectives. To balance adequacy and completeness in the scenario analysis, it is recommended to include 9–15 objectives for the development of descriptors and variants in Step 2, in line with the methodological guidelines of Weimer-Jehle, (2023). By addressing these critical elements, this step provides a structured and goal-oriented process fostering clarity, alignment, and a shared vision among all stakeholders.

Figure 1: Stepwise approach for combining cross-impact balance analysis (CIB), AHP and the Fuzzy TOPSIS methods

3.2 STEP 2: DEVELOP DESCRIPTORS AND VARIANTS

The CIB method uses systems theory and formal logic to create internally consistent scenarios based on interacting drivers of change, integrating both qualitative and quantitative inputs (Weimer-Jehle, 2006). A key step in this process is identifying descriptors; ‘critical factors defining the system’ and their associated variants, which represent specific states these factors can assume (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). Descriptors should be developed at a high aggregation level (Weimer-Jehle, 2023), with each descriptor representing one objective, that can be supported by related criteria and / or a narrative that explains the descriptor's role and significance within the system. Variants then enable systematic exploration of

scenarios by capturing the range of possible outcomes for each descriptor. For example, in adaptive reuse projects, "Environmental impact" could be a descriptor for the objective: ‘Reducing environmental impact of the building’, with variants such as "Low," "Medium," and "High." Stakeholders are encouraged to assign descriptive names and narratives to variants for clarity and effective communication, keeping 2–4 variants per descriptor as recommended by (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). The CIB analysis requirements of completeness (descriptor variants must cover all possible futures), mutual exclusivity (each development aligns with only one variant), and absence of overlap (variants of different descriptors must address distinct topics) should also be taken into account when developing variants (Weimer-Jehle, 2023).

Although the CIB methodology supports variants with various characteristics (ordinal, nominal, or ratio) this paper focuses on descriptors with ordinal measurement scales. For instance, "user demand" as a descriptor might include ordinal variants like "Low," "Medium," and "High," reflecting their ranked importance. This approach simplifies the system, making it possible to translate qualitative ordinal variants into linguistic variables essential for integration with the Fuzzy TOPSIS method. Using ordinal descriptors ensures consistency in both the CIB analysis and fuzzy TOPSIS methods, enabling structured evaluation of interactions and their influence on adaptive reuse scenario outcomes.

3.3 STEP 3: IDENTIFY RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN DESCRIPTORS AND VARIANTS

Identifying the interrelationships between descriptor variants is critical in Cross-Impact Balance (CIB) analysis, as it ensures the logical coherence and plausibility of the scenarios generated (Weimer-Jehle, 2023). These interrelationships capture how one variant influences or is influenced by another, reflecting the underlying dynamics of the system. Without this step, the analysis risks inconsistencies or contradictions, undermining the reliability of the scenarios (Weimer-Jehle, 2023).

To identify these relationships, the scale recommended by (Weimer-Jehle, 2006) provides a structured and systematic approach. This scale uses a range from -3 to +3 to denote the influence of one variant on another: +3 indicates a strong positive impact, 0 signifies no impact, and -3 represents a strong negative impact. These values are assigned within a cross-impact matrix, ensuring all potential interactions are considered (Table 1). This elicitation of data can be conducted in a participatory group setting with stakeholders, fostering collaboration and shared understanding. Alternatively, other methods such as expert surveys (Weimer-Jehle et al., 2012), Delphi techniques (Tori et al., 2023), or literature reviews (Weimer-Jehle, 2023), can be employed to gather the required input systematically. By following this method, the CIB process produces scenarios that are not only internally consistent but also reflective of the real-world,

in the decision-making process. The CR is calculated using Equation (4):

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \quad (4)$$

The Consistency Index (CI) is a key metric in the AHP used to measure the logical coherence of judgments in pairwise comparison matrices, while the Random Index (RI) represents the average CI derived from 500 reciprocal matrices populated with values from Saaty's fundamental 1–9 scale (Saaty, 1990). The RI varies based on the number of criteria in a matrix, as outlined in Table (2). The CI is calculated using Equation (5):

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} \quad (5)$$

where λ_{max} is the maximum eigenvalue of the comparison matrix, and n is the number of objectives. To compute the eigenvalue for a pairwise comparison matrix in AHP, multiply the pairwise comparison matrix M by the priority vector w using Equation (6):

$$M * w = \lambda_{max} * w \quad (6)$$

Here, w represents the normalized priority weights of the criteria. For each row i in the resulting matrix $A * w$ computed by using Equation (7):

$$\lambda_i = \frac{(A * w)_i}{w_i} \quad (7)$$

Where $(A * w)_i$ is the i -th element of the resulting vector, and w_i is the i -th element of the priority vector. The maximum eigenvalue of the comparison matrix is then calculated by taking the average value of all λ_i , Where n is the number of objectives using Equation (8):

$$\lambda_{max} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i}{n} \quad (8)$$

The consistency check is essential to ensure that judgments are logically consistent, as inconsistencies can compromise the validity of the decision-making process, leading to unreliable outcomes. This process reinforces robust decision-making by encouraging stakeholders to critically evaluate their judgments, ensuring coherence and reliability throughout the analysis.

Table 2: Random Index (RI) for different numbers of objectives (Saaty, 1990)

Number of criteria	Random Index (RI)
2	0
3	0.58
4	0.90
5	1.12

3.6 STEP 6: CONSTRUCT THE WEIGHTED FUZZY DECISION MATRIX

Following the elicitation of decision-makers' preferences through the AHP method, the subsequent step involves conducting decision analysis utilizing the Fuzzy TOPSIS method. The Fuzzy TOPSIS method is an extension of the traditional Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) that incorporates fuzzy set theory to handle uncertainty and vagueness in decision-making (Chen, 2000). This approach is particularly useful when preferences are expressed in qualitative terms, such as linguistic variables, which are subjective and imprecise by nature, such as with scenarios in the CIB analysis. Fuzzy sets enable the representation of linguistic variables such as "Low," "Medium," and "High" as fuzzy numbers. Among the different forms of fuzzy sets, triangular fuzzy numbers (TFNs) are most commonly used due to their simplicity and computational efficiency (Chen, 2000). A triangular fuzzy number is represented as $\tilde{A}_{ij} = (l_{ij}, m_{ij}, u_{ij})$ where l is the lower bound, m is the most likely value, and u is the upper bound, forming a triangular membership function. A fuzzy number \tilde{A} on R is defined as a triangular fuzzy number (TFN) if its membership function $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x) : R \rightarrow [0,1]$ is expressed as follows in Equation (9):

$$\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x-l}{m-l}, & l \leq x \leq m \\ \frac{u-x}{u-m}, & m \leq x \leq u \\ 0, & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

To convert linguistic variables into fuzzy numbers, a predefined fuzzy scale should be developed which assigns specific TFNs to each linguistic term based on expert judgment or domain knowledge. This allows qualitative assessments to be transformed into quantitative data that can be processed within the Fuzzy TOPSIS framework, enabling a more nuanced and flexible evaluation of scenarios under uncertainty. A fuzzy scale is employed to transform the qualitative ordinal variants from the consistent scenarios in Step 4 into fuzzy numbers, which are subsequently used to construct the decision matrix.

Following the fuzzification process, construct the fuzzy pairwise decision matrix by first calculating the relative importance of each objective (w_j) following step 5, using Equation (10):

$$\tilde{V} = \tilde{A}_{ij} \times w_j = (l_{ij} * w_j * m_{ij} * w_j * u_{ij} * w_j) \quad (10)$$

The overall weighted fuzzy decision matrix can then be constructed using Equation (11), Where: m is the number of scenarios, and n is the number of objectives.

$$\tilde{V} = \begin{bmatrix} (l_{11} * w_1, m_{11} * w_1, u_{11} * w_1) & \cdots & (l_{1n} * w_n, m_{1n} * w_n, u_{1n} * w_n) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ (l_{m1} * w_1, m_{m1} * w_1, u_{m1} * w_1) & \cdots & (l_{mn} * w_n, m_{mn} * w_n, u_{mn} * w_n) \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

3.7 STEP 7: NORMALIZE THE WEIGHTED FUZZY DECISION MATRIX

To normalize the weighted fuzzy decision matrix \tilde{V} , each objective $\tilde{V}_{ij} = (l_{ij}, m_{ij}, u_{ij})$ is normalized based on the type of objective (benefit or cost). For benefit objectives (higher values are preferred) Equation (12) can be used:

$$\bar{R}_{ij} = \left(\frac{l_{ij}}{u_j^+}, \frac{m_{ij}}{u_j^+}, \frac{u_{ij}}{u_j^+} \right) \quad (12)$$

For the cost criteria (lower values are preferred) Equation (13) is used:

$$\bar{R}_{ij} = \left(\frac{l_j^-}{u_{ij}}, \frac{m_j^-}{m_{ij}}, \frac{u_j^-}{l_{ij}} \right) \quad (13)$$

Where u_j^+ is the maximum upper bound for the j -th objective, and l_j^- is the minimum lower bound for the j -th objective.

3.8 STEP 8: DETERMINE THE FUZZY POSITIVE-IDEAL SOLUTION (FPIS) AND FUZZY NEGATIVE-IDEAL SOLUTION (FNIS)

In the Fuzzy TOPSIS method, the FPIS (Fuzzy Positive Ideal Solution) represents the optimal fuzzy values for each objective, while the FNIS (Fuzzy Negative Ideal Solution) reflects the least desirable outcomes. These are determined by identifying the best and worst fuzzy scores across all scenarios for each objective. Scenarios are ranked based on their proximity to the FPIS and distance from the FNIS, with the closest scenario to the FPIS and farthest from the FNIS considered the best choice.

If x_{ij} represents the fuzzy evaluation of the i -th alternative with respect to the j -th objective, the FPIS for each criterion can be represented as:

$$A_j^+ = \begin{cases} \max_i x_{ij} & \text{if the objective is beneficial} \\ \min_i x_{ij} & \text{if the objective is non-beneficial} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Conversely, if x_{ij} represents the fuzzy evaluation of the i -th alternative with respect to the j -th objective, the FNIS for each objective can be represented as:

$$A_j^- = \begin{cases} \min_i x_{ij} & \text{if the objective is beneficial} \\ \max_i x_{ij} & \text{if the objective is non-beneficial} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

3.9 STEP 9: CALCULATE THE DISTANCE OF EACH SCENARIO FROM FPIS AND FNIS

The distances from each scenario to the FPIS (d_i^*) and FNIS (d_i^-) are calculated using the fuzzy distance measure: Euclidian distance using Equation (16).

The distance d between two fuzzy numbers $\tilde{A}_1 = (l_1, m_1, u_1)$ and $\tilde{A}_2 = (l_2, m_2, u_2)$ is:

$$d(\tilde{A}_1, \tilde{A}_2) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{3} [(l_1 - l_2)^2 + (m_1 - m_2)^2 + (u_1 - u_2)^2]} \quad (16)$$

To calculate the distances from FPIS and FNIS to each scenario the following Equations (17&18) can be used:

Distance from FPIS:

$$(d_i^+) : d_i^+ \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (\bar{R}_{ij} - \tilde{A}_j^+)^2} \quad (17)$$

Distance from FNIS

$$(d_i^-) : d_i^- \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (\bar{R}_{ij} - \tilde{A}_j^-)^2} \quad (18)$$

Here, n is the number of objectives, x_{ij} is the fuzzy score of the i -th scenario on the j -th objective, and A_j^+ is the score of the FPIS on the j -th objective, and A_j^- is the score of the FNIS on the j -th objective. Using these distances, each scenario's relative closeness to the ideal solution is calculated, which is used to rank the scenarios. The alternative with the shortest distance to the FPIS and the longest distance from the FNIS is considered the optimal choice.

3.10 STEP 10: OBTAIN THE CLOSENNESS COEFFICIENTS OF EACH SCENARIO

In the Fuzzy TOPSIS method, the closeness indicator is a metric for ranking scenarios by measuring their proximity to the Fuzzy Positive Ideal Solution (FPIS) and their distance from the Fuzzy Negative Ideal Solution (FNIS). This ranking provides decision makers with a clear understanding of which scenario best aligns with their preferences and objectives. By summarizing each scenario's performance across all objectives, the closeness indicator supports informed, consensus-driven decisions, highlighting not only the best options but also how closely each one approaches the ideal conditions. The closeness indicator is calculated by using the following Equation (19):

$$CC_i = \frac{d_i^-}{d_i^+ + d_i^-} \quad (19)$$

Where d_i^+ is the distance of the i -th alternative from the FPIS, and d_i^- is its distance from the FNIS. The closeness indicator, CC_i , ranges from 0 to 1, where a value closer to 1 indicates that the scenario is closer to the FPIS and farther from the FNIS, making it a more preferable option.

4 HYPOTHETICAL EXAMPLE

The application of the newly introduced mixed-method approach is demonstrated using a hypothetical example of an adaptive reuse project.

4.1 STEP 1: DEFINE THE AIM AND OBJECTIVES

For the hypothetical example we have developed the following aim, objectives and criteria. For the selection of the objectives and criteria we have drawn inspiration from van Laar et al., (2024), who conducted an extensive literature review on criteria and objectives in the decision-making process of adaptive reuse. For practical reasons we have limited the number of objectives to five.

Table 3: The project aim and objectives of the hypothetical example

Project Aim	The aim of this project is to adaptively reuse an existing building to meet functional, environmental, and social needs while preserving its historical, significance.
Objectives	O1) To increase social impact
	O2) To reduce environmental impact
	O3) To reduce cost
	O4) To improve the physical quality and durability of the building
	O5) To preserve the historic and cultural value of the building

4.2 STEP 2: DEVELOP DESCRIPTORS AND VARIANTS

Based on the objectives chosen, comprehensive descriptors and variants were developed that included names, description, objective and criteria (Appendix A). For all descriptors, 3 ordinal variants were drawn up: a strong variant in which the objective within the descriptor is definitely reached, a medium variant in which the objective is partially reached, and a weak variant in which the objective is not reached.

The same linguistic variables were chosen for each objective to simplify the FUZZY translation in Step 6.

An example for the descriptor Social impact is provided in Table (4).

Table 4: The descriptor: "Social Impact" and its corresponding variants

Descriptor: Social Impact		Variants
Objective	To increase social Impact	<p>A1: Social Heaven (strong variant) The adaptive reuse project enhances social impact by addressing socio-economic factors like house prices, gentrification, and perceived safety while boosting neighbourhood liveability. It fosters social cohesion by serving as a community hub and improves surrounding public spaces.</p> <p>A2: Socially Acceptable (medium variant) The adaptive reuse project avoids negative socio-economic impacts, with some focus on enhancing public spaces and liveability. While not central to fostering community, it offers spaces for social interaction.</p> <p>A3: Socially Limited (weak variant) The adaptive reuse project negatively impacts socio-economic conditions, potentially raising housing prices and driving gentrification. It fails to improve liveability, public spaces, or social cohesion.</p>
	Social cohesion Public spaces Liveability Socio-economic conditions	

4.3 STEP 3: IDENTIFY RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN DESCRIPTORS AND VARIANTS

We have mapped the interactions between all descriptor-variant combinations using the scale from Weimer-Jehle, (2006). This resulted in the following Cross-impact balance matrix (Table 5):

Table 5: The completed CIB matrix for the hypothetical example

CIB Matrix	A) Social Impact			B) Environmental Impact			C) Cost			D) Physical quality			E) Historic and Cultural value					
	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2	B3	C1	C2	C3	D1	D2	D3	E1	E2	E3			
A) Social Impact: A1) Social heaven A2) Socially acceptable A3) Socially limited				3	2	-2	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	-2			
				2	1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	-1			
				-2	-1	2	-1	0	1	-1	0	1	0	0	0	-2	0	2
B) Environmental Impact: B1) Sustainability heaven B2) Environmentally friendly B3) Environmentally unfriendly	2	1	0				-3	-1	3	0	0	0	0	-1	0			
	0	0	0				-1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	-1
	-2	-1	1				-1	1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
C) Cost: C1) Cost Efficient C2) Moderately costly C3) Very costly	1	1	-1	-1	2	1				3	2	1	-2	-1	2			
	0	0	0	-1	2	1				1	0	-1	1	0	-1	1	1	0
	-2	-1	1	2	-2	2				2	1	-2	2	1	-2	-3	-1	3
D) Physical quality: D1) Strong and Durable D2) Sufficiently durable D3) Poor building quality	1	0	0	3	2	0	2	-1	-2				3	2	-2			
	0	0	0	2	1	0	1	1	-1				2	1	0	2	1	0
	0	0	1	-2	0	1	-2	1	2				-3	-1	2	-3	-1	2
E) Historic/Cultural value E1) Preserving History E2) Attention to history E3) Ignoring history	2	1	-1	-1	0	0	-2	-1	2	3	2	-2						
	1	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	1	2	1	-1				1	1	-1
	-2	-1	2	1	0	0	1	0	-1	-1	0	2				-1	0	2
Impact Sum	6	3	-2	4	6	-1	-2	-3	3	6	4	-1	4	2	-2			

4.4 STEP 4: CONSTRUCT SCENARIOS

The consistency analysis was performed using the Scenario Wizard software, with a consistency value of 1 following Equation (1). This resulted in 4 consistent scenarios that are included for decision analysis (Figure 2). Each scenario consists of a consistent combination of variants that is characterised by strong (green), medium (yellow), or weak (red) in relation to the objective of the descriptor.

Scenario No. 1	Scenario No. 2	Scenario No. 3	Scenario No. 4
Social Impact: Social heaven	Social Impact: Socially limited		
Environmental Impact: Sustainability heaven	Environmental Impact: Environmentally unfriendly	Environmental Impact: Sustainability heaven	Environmental Impact: Environmentally unfriendly
Cost: Very costly	Cost: Moderately costly	Cost: Very costly	Cost: Moderately costly
Physical quality: Strong and Durable			Physical quality: Poor building quality
Historic and Cultural value: Preserving History	Historic and Cultural value: Attention to history	Historic and Cultural value: Ignoring history	

Figure 2: The scenario tableau for the hypothetical example

4.5 STEP 5: DETERMINING THE WEIGHTS OF THE OBJECTIVES

We determined the weights of the objectives through the AHP methodology by using the Saaty's 9-point Likert scale (Saaty, 1990). The relative importance of the objectives is displayed in the pairwise comparison matrix:

$$M = \begin{matrix} O_1 \\ O_2 \\ O_3 \\ O_4 \\ O_5 \end{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} O_1 & O_2 & O_3 & O_4 & O_5 \\ 1 & (3) & (5) & (7) & (9) \\ (0.33) & 1 & (3) & (5) & (7) \\ (0.2) & (0.33) & 1 & (3) & (5) \\ (0.14) & (0.2) & (0.33) & 1 & (3) \\ (0.11) & (0.14) & (0.2) & (0.33) & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

The pairwise comparison matrix was normalized by dividing each entry by the sum of its column using Equation (3), which results in the normalized pairwise comparison matrix: Equation (21).

$$M_n = \begin{matrix} O_1 \\ O_2 \\ O_3 \\ O_4 \\ O_5 \end{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} O_1 & O_2 & O_3 & O_4 & O_5 \\ (0.520) & (0.545) & (0.476) & (0.437) & (0.400) \\ (0.173) & (0.182) & (0.286) & (0.312) & (0.311) \\ (0.104) & (0.061) & (0.095) & (0.188) & (0.222) \\ (0.073) & (0.036) & (0.032) & (0.062) & (0.133) \\ (0.057) & (0.027) & (0.019) & (0.041) & (0.089) \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

The relative weight w_k of each objective was calculated by averaging the normalized values across each row. Table (6). presents the final weights. The objective "To reduce cost" is the most important, while the objective "To increase social impact" is the least important.

Table 6: The weights for each objective following AHP

Objective (O_n)	Weight (w_k)
To reduce cost (O_3)	0.476
To preserve the historic & cultural value of the building (O_5)	0.253
To improve the physical quality/durability of the building (O_4)	0.134
To reduce environmental impact (O_2)	0.067
To increase social impact (O_1)	0.045

To ensure the judgments were consistent, the largest eigenvalue was computed using Equation (22) along with the Consistency Index (CI); Equation (23) and Consistency Ratio (CR); Equation (24):

Largest Eigenvalue:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{max} &= \frac{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5}{5} \\ &= \frac{5.83 + 5.78 + 5.51 + 5.42 + 4.07}{5} \\ \lambda_{max} &= 5.333 \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Consistency Index (CI):

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} = \frac{5.333 - 5}{5 - 1} = 0.083 \quad (23)$$

The Random Index (RI) value with 5 objectives is: 1.12 (Table 2).

Consistency Ratio (CR)

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} = \frac{0.083}{1.12} = 0.074 \quad (24)$$

The Consistency Ratio (CR) = 0.074 is below the threshold of 0.1, indicating that the pairwise comparison matrix is acceptably consistent.

4.6 STEP 6: CONSTRUCT THE WEIGHTED FUZZY DECISION MATRIX

The decision matrix D with linguistic variables is constructed based on the outcome of the consistency analysis from Step 4 (Figure 2), with S_n being the scenarios; Equation (25).

$$D = \begin{matrix} O_1 \\ O_2 \\ O_3 \\ O_4 \\ O_5 \end{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} S_1 & S_2 & S_3 & S_4 \\ Strong & Weak & Weak & Weak \\ Strong & Weak & Strong & Weak \\ Weak & Medium & Weak & Medium \\ Strong & Strong & Strong & Weak \\ Strong & Medium & Weak & Weak \end{bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

To transform the linguistic decision matrix into a fuzzy matrix, the following conversion scale is used that incorporates triangular fuzzy numbers (Table 7).

Table 7: The linguistic variable conversion table

Linguistic variable	Corresponding triangular fuzzy numbers (l, m, u)
Weak	(1,3,5)
Medium	(3,5,7)
Strong	(5,7,9)

After conversion the following fuzzy decision matrix D_f was constructed using Equation (26):

$$D_f = \begin{matrix} O_1 \\ O_2 \\ O_3 \\ O_4 \\ O_5 \end{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} S_1 & S_2 & S_3 & S_4 \\ (5,7,9) & (1,3,5) & (1,3,5) & (1,3,5) \\ (5,7,9) & (1,3,5) & (5,7,9) & (1,3,5) \\ (1,3,5) & (3,5,7) & (1,3,5) & (3,5,7) \\ (5,7,9) & (5,7,9) & (5,7,9) & (1,3,5) \\ (5,7,9) & (3,5,7) & (1,3,5) & (1,3,5) \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

To arrive at the weighted fuzzy decision matrix the relative weights of the objectives w_k were multiplied with the triangular fuzzy numbers (Table 8):

4.7 STEP 7: NORMALIZE THE WEIGHTED FUZZY DECISION MATRIX

Using Equation (12) we can then normalize the weighted fuzzy decision matrix (Table 9).

Table 8: The weighted fuzzy decision matrix for the hypothetical example

	Scenario 1 (S_1)	Scenario 2 (S_2)	Scenario 3 (S_3)	Scenario 4 (S_4)
Social Impact (O_1)	(0.225, 0.315, 0.405)	(0.045, 0.135, 0.225)	(0.045, 0.135, 0.225)	(0.045, 0.135, 0.225)
Environmental impact (O_2)	(0.335, 0.469, 0.603)	(0.067, 0.201, 0.335)	(0.335, 0.469, 0.603)	(0.067, 0.201, 0.335)
Cost (O_3)	(0.476, 1.428, 2.380)	(1.428, 2.380, 3.332)	(0.476, 1.428, 2.380)	(1.428, 2.380, 3.332)
Physical quality (O_4)	(0.670, 0.938, 1.206)	(0.670, 0.938, 1.206)	(0.670, 0.938, 1.206)	(0.134, 0.402, 0.670)
Historic/ cultural value (O_5)	(1.265, 1.771, 2.277)	(0.759, 1.265, 1.771)	(0.253, 0.759, 1.265)	(0.253, 0.759, 1.265)

Table 9: The normalized weighted fuzzy decision matrix for the hypothetical example

	Scenario 1 (S_1)	Scenario 2 (S_2)	Scenario 3 (S_3)	Scenario 4 (S_4)
Social Impact (O_1)	(0.095, 0.132, 0.170)	(0.014, 0.041, 0.068)	(0.019, 0.057, 0.095)	(0.014, 0.041, 0.068)
Environmental impact (O_2)	(0.141, 0.197, 0.253)	(0.020, 0.060, 0.101)	(0.141, 0.197, 0.253)	(0.020, 0.060, 0.101)
Cost (O_3)	(0.200, 0.600, 1.000)	(0.429, 0.714, 1.000)	(0.200, 0.600, 1.000)	(0.429, 0.714, 1.000)
Physical quality (O_4)	(0.282, 0.394, 0.507)	(0.201, 0.282, 0.362)	(0.282, 0.394, 0.507)	(0.040, 0.121, 0.201)
Historic/ cultural value (O_5)	(0.532, 0.744, 0.957)	(0.228, 0.380, 0.532)	(0.106, 0.319, 0.532)	(0.076, 0.228, 0.380)

4.8 STEP 8: DETERMINE THE FUZZY POSITIVE-IDEAL SOLUTION (FPIS) AND FUZZY NEGATIVE-IDEAL SOLUTION (FNIS)

Using the normalized weighted fuzzy decision matrix from Step 7 (Table 9), the FPIS and FNIS were calculated for each objective using Equation 14 and 15 resulting in Table (10).

Table 10: The FPIS and FNIS values for each objective in the hypothetical example

Objectives (O_n)	FPIS	FNIS
Social Impact (O_1)	(0.095, 0.132, 0.170)	(0.014, 0.041, 0.068)
Environmental impact (O_2)	(0.141, 0.197, 0.253)	(0.020, 0.060, 0.101)
Cost (O_3)	(0.429, 0.714, 1.000)	(0.200, 0.600, 1.000)
Physical quality (O_4)	(0.282, 0.394, 0.507)	(0.040, 0.121, 0.201)
Historic/ cultural value (O_5)	(0.532, 0.744, 0.957)	(0.076, 0.228, 0.380)

4.9 STEP 9: CALCULATE THE DISTANCE OF EACH SCENARIO FROM FPIS AND FNIS

Using the Euclidean distance each scenario from the FPIS and FNIS were computed using Equation (16). Distances were calculated for each scenario based on the FPIS D^+ and FNIS D^- (Table 11).

Table 11: The distance from each scenario to the FPIS and FNIS

Scenario (S_n)	D^+ (FPIS Distance)	D^- (FNIS Distance)
Scenario 1 (S_1)	0.543	0.802
Scenario 2 (S_2)	0.786	0.617
Scenario 3 (S_3)	0.643	0.732
Scenario 4 (S_4)	0.849	0.503

4.10 STEP 10: OBTAIN THE CLOSENESS COEFFICIENTS OF EACH SCENARIO

Once the distances from FPIS and FNIS are determined, the Closeness Coefficients can be obtained using Equation (27). An example calculation for Scenario 2 is given:

$$CC_i = \frac{d_i^-}{d_i^+ + d_i^-} = \frac{0.617}{0.786 + 0.617} = 0.440 \quad (27)$$

This results in the following scenario ranking, with scenario 1 ultimately ranking on top (Table 12).

Table 12: The Closeness Coefficient for each scenario

Scenario (S_n)	Closeness Coefficient CC_n	Rank
Scenario 1 (S_1)	0.596	1
Scenario 2 (S_2)	0.440	3
Scenario 3 (S_3)	0.532	2
Scenario 4 (S_4)	0.372	4

5 CONCLUSION AND REMARKS

This study has introduced an integrated decision-making framework that combines Cross-Impact Balance (CIB) analysis, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), and Fuzzy-TOPSIS to enhance scenario development and multi-criteria evaluation in adaptive reuse projects. By incorporating scenario-based methodologies within a structured decision-making process, this approach enables stakeholders to systematically explore future-oriented reuse options while addressing uncertainty, complexity, and competing priorities. The framework was demonstrated through a hypothetical adaptive reuse project, illustrating how these methods interact to generate, assess, and rank consistent scenarios.

The findings highlight the benefits of integrating different methodologies to strengthen decision-making. CIB analysis ensures scenario consistency, reducing the likelihood of incoherent or contradictory planning outcomes. AHP provides a structured means to weight stakeholder preferences, ensuring that diverse perspectives are reflected in the evaluation process. Meanwhile, Fuzzy-TOPSIS offers a robust ranking mechanism that accounts for uncertainty, allowing decision-makers to prioritize alternatives more effectively. The integration of these methods enhances future-oriented decision-making by ensuring that adaptive reuse strategies consider long-term sustainability, economic feasibility, and social impact rather than being constrained by immediate limitations. Additionally, the approach fosters stakeholder engagement and transparency by actively involving participants in defining objectives, developing descriptors, and evaluating scenarios, leading to a more inclusive and aligned decision-making process. The structured methodology also enhances practical applicability, making it adaptable for real-world projects where trade-offs must be assessed, and priorities established.

Despite its advantages, certain limitations should be acknowledged. The methodology relies significantly on subjective inputs, particularly in scenario development and the conversion of linguistic variables in the Fuzzy-TOPSIS method. Its effectiveness depends on the ability of stakeholders and experts to define meaningful descriptors and variants, assess interactions accurately, and translate qualitative insights into quantitative measures. Any inconsistencies or biases in these subjective judgments could influence the final rankings. Moreover, for the methodology to function effectively, it is crucial to ensure active stakeholder participation at multiple stages, including defining objectives, developing scenario descriptors, weighting criteria, and ranking scenarios. Without sufficient engagement, the approach risks overlooking critical real-world considerations and diminishing the legitimacy of its outcomes. Future research should explore participatory mechanisms to strengthen stakeholder involvement and ensure a balanced representation of perspectives.

5.1 FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

To further validate the proposed approach, real-world case studies should be conducted to test its practical applicability. Future research could also focus on:

- Improving the linguistic variable conversion process by developing standardized fuzzy scales that minimize subjectivity.
- Automating parts of the methodology to reduce the complexity of data input and improve usability.
- Exploring hybrid decision-support tools that integrate participatory scenario development with computational methods to enhance consistency and scalability.

The proposed framework demonstrates the potential of integrating scenario planning and multi-criteria decision-making, yet its full impact can only be realized through real-world applications. As the built environment continues to evolve, future efforts should focus on refining participatory methods and optimizing decision-support tools to promote practical applicability, ensuring that adaptive reuse strategies are data-driven, inclusive, and aligned with long-term sustainability goals.

REFERENCES

- Amer, M., Daim, T. U., & Jetter, A. (2013). A review of scenario planning. *Futures*, 46, 23–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2012.10.003>
- Bottero, M., Datola, G., Fazzari, D., & Ingaramo, R. (2022). Re-Thinking Detroit: A Multicriteria-Based Approach for Adaptive Reuse for the Corktown District. *Sustainability*, 14(14), Article 14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14148343>
- Chen, C.-T. (2000). Extensions of the TOPSIS for group decision-making under fuzzy environment. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 114(1), 1–9. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-0114\(97\)00377-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-0114(97)00377-1)
- Conejos, S. (2013). Optimisation of future building adaptive reuse design criteria for urban sustainability. *Journal of Design Research*, 11(3), 225–242.
- Dang, V. T., Wang, J., & Dang, W. V.-T. (2019). An Integrated Fuzzy AHP and Fuzzy TOPSIS Approach to Assess Sustainable Urban Development in an Emerging Economy. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(16), Article 16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16162902>
- Della Spina, L. (2020). Adaptive Sustainable Reuse for Cultural Heritage: A Multiple Criteria Decision Aiding Approach Supporting Urban Development Processes. *Sustainability*, 12(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12041363>
- Efe, B. (2016). An integrated fuzzy multi criteria group decision making approach for ERP system selection. *Applied Soft Computing*, 38, 106–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asoc.2015.09.037>
- Foster, G. (2020). Circular economy strategies for adaptive reuse of cultural heritage buildings to reduce environmental impacts. *Resources, Conservation and*

- Recycling*, 152, 104507. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104507>
- Gassner, R., & Steinmüller, K. (2018). *Scenarios that tell a Story. Normative Narrative Scenarios – An Efficient Tool for Participative Innovation-Oriented Foresight*. 37–48. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-25074-4_3
- Greco, A., van Laar, B., Remøy, H., & Gruis, V. (2024). Accelerating circularity systemically: Three directions for impactful research. *Npj Urban Sustainability*, 4(1), 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42949-024-00183-8>
- Love, P. E. D., Ika, L. A., & Pinto, J. K. (2023). Fast-and-frugal heuristics for decision-making in uncertain and complex settings in construction. *Developments in the Built Environment*, 14, 100129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dibe.2023.100129>
- Mathew, M., Chakraborty, R. K., & Ryan, M. J. (2020). A novel approach integrating AHP and TOPSIS under spherical fuzzy sets for advanced manufacturing system selection. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 96, 103988. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2020.103988>
- Nadkarni, R. R., & Puthuvayi, B. (2020). A comprehensive literature review of Multi-Criteria Decision Making methods in heritage buildings. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 32. Scopus. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2020.101814>
- Nedeljkovic, D., Jurenic, T., & Djokic, L. (2023). Comparative analysis of multi-criteria models for decision-making in the process of building adaptation. *Heliyon*, 9(6), e16620. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16620>
- Patil, S. K., & Kant, R. (2014). A fuzzy AHP-TOPSIS framework for ranking the solutions of Knowledge Management adoption in Supply Chain to overcome its barriers. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 41(2), 679–693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2013.07.093>
- Rowe, E., Wright, G., & Derbyshire, J. (2017). Enhancing horizon scanning by utilizing pre-developed scenarios: Analysis of current practice and specification of a process improvement to aid the identification of important ‘weak signals’. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 125, 224–235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2017.08.001>
- Saaty, T. L. (1990). How to make a decision: The analytic hierarchy process. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 48(1), 9–26. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-2217\(90\)90057-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-2217(90)90057-1)
- Sahoo, S. K., & Goswami, S. S. (2023). A comprehensive review of multiple criteria decision-making (MCDM) Methods: Advancements, applications, and future directions. *Decision Making Advances*, 1(1), 25–48.
- Sanchez, B., Esnaashary Esfahani, M., & Haas, C. (2019). A methodology to analyze the net environmental impacts and building’s cost performance of an adaptive reuse project: A case study of the Waterloo County Courthouse renovations. *Environment Systems and Decisions*, 39(4), 419–438. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10669-019-09734-2>
- Shahi, S., Esnaashary Esfahani, M., Bachmann, C., Haas, C. (2020). A definition framework for building adaptation projects. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2020.102345>
- Stewart, T. J., French, S., & Rios, J. (2013). Integrating multicriteria decision analysis and scenario planning—Review and extension. *Omega*, 41(4), 679–688. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2012.09.003>
- Symstad, A. J., Fisichelli, N. A., Miller, B. W., Rowland, E., & Schuurman, G. W. (2017). Multiple methods for multiple futures: Integrating qualitative scenario planning and quantitative simulation modeling for natural resource decision making. *Climate Risk Management*, 17, 78–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2017.07.002>
- Tori, S., te Boveldt, G., Keseru, I., & Macharis, C. (2023). Brussels mobility in 2050: Participatory mixed-method scenario building to explore alternative futures. *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 22, 100919. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2023.100919>
- van Laar, B., Greco, A., Remøy, H., & Gruis, V. (2024). What matters when? – An integrative literature review on decision criteria in different stages of the adaptive reuse process. *Developments in the Built Environment*, 100439. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dibe.2024.100439>
- van Notten, P. W. F., Rotmans, J., van Asselt, M. B. A., & Rothman, D. S. (2003). An updated scenario typology. *Futures*, 35(5), 423–443. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-3287\(02\)00090-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-3287(02)00090-3)
- Vardopoulos, I., Tsilika, E., Sarantakou, E., Zorpas, A. A., Salvati, L., & Tsartas, P. (2021). An Integrated SWOT-PESTLE-AHP Model Assessing Sustainability in Adaptive Reuse Projects. *Applied Sciences*, 11(15), Article 15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11157134>
- Weimer-Jehle, W. (2006). Cross-impact balances: A system-theoretical approach to cross-impact analysis. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 73(4), 334–361. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2005.06.005>
- Weimer-Jehle, W. (2023). *Cross-Impact Balances (CIB) for Scenario Analysis: Fundamentals and Implementation*. Springer Nature Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-27230-1>
- Weimer-Jehle, W., Deuschle, J., & Rehaag, R. (2012). Familial and societal causes of juvenile obesity—A qualitative model on obesity development and prevention in socially disadvantaged children and adolescents. *Journal of Public Health*, 20(2), 111–124. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10389-011-0473-8>
- Wilkinson, S. (2014). The preliminary assessment of adaptation potential in existing office buildings. *International Journal of Strategic Property Management*, 18, 77–87. <https://doi.org/10.3846/1648715X.2013.853705>
- Yung, E. H. K., & Chan, E. H. W. (2012). Implementation challenges to the adaptive reuse of heritage buildings: Towards the goals of sustainable, low carbon cities. *Habitat International*, 36(3), 352–361. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.habitatint.2011.11.001>